

A QUANTUM MODEL FOR SOUND SYNTHESIS: QHOSYN

Rodney DuPlessis

UCSB

rodney@rodneyduplessis.com

ABSTRACT

The dynamic nature of quantum physical models make them well-suited to creative sound design and musical purposes through sonification and metaphor. These systems outline a new class of time-varying stochastic physical models. QHOSYN is a software synthesizer for simulating and sonifying the most fundamental of quantum mechanical models: the quantum harmonic oscillator. This basic model is used in physics to describe a plethora of more complex systems, and so it serves as a solid foundation for work in sonifying quantum systems. QHOSYN runs on Linux, Windows, and MacOS and allows composers and music researchers to explore the sonic potential in this physical model. In this paper, the software is introduced through a discussion of its background, an overview of the physical simulation implementation, a look at the visual interface, a description of the internal sound engine and how it can be extended through OSC, and finally a case study of using the software in composition.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dennis Gabor was the first to suggest a quantum notion of sound [1, 2]. Inspired by this, Iannis Xenakis developed a theory for music composition using sound grains [3]. Xenakis conceived of arranging these sound grains according to probabilistic laws derived from information theory and thermodynamics. Later, Curtis Roads greatly expanded the theory of microsound and granular synthesis [4]. Much of this work in formalizing a granular approach to sound focused on the novel idea of treating sound as a mass of particles. This has opened an enormous field of possibilities in sound analysis, synthesis, and composition [5]. Conversely to how treating an elementary particle as a wave was a paradigm shift for physicists in the early 20th century, treating the traditionally wave-like phenomenon of sound as a particle was a novel concept for musicians in the late-20th century.

The research presented here returns to Gabor's original meaning by treating sound as quantum particles in the most literal sense. These quantum particles, described by the mathematics of quantum mechanics, are well known to exhibit characteristics of both particles and waves, to

defy causality, and to exist in superpositions of probability states. Using this kind of entity and the mathematics of quantum physics in sonification can lead to novel and compelling musical material¹.

The idea of using quantum physical simulations in music has seen fairly little exploration aside from Rajmil Fischmann's Erwin software [6] and a piece by Bob Sturm [7]. The Allosphere Research Group, led by JoAnn Kuchera-Morin, has done some of the most compelling work to date in sonifying and visualizing quantum processes [8].

QHOSYN (Quantum Harmonic Oscillator Synthesizer; pronounced as "cosine") was created to simulate a quantum harmonic oscillator for the purpose of exploring the possibilities of sonifying such a system. Like its counterpart in classical mechanics, the quantum harmonic oscillator is a fundamental model in quantum mechanics as it forms the basis of many systems [9]. Unlike the classical harmonic oscillator, the quantum harmonic oscillator describes a time-varying wavefunction, rather than a classical object. The ground state of this wave, like all quantum systems, is greater than zero. In other words, it cannot be totally static and must always be in some state of fluctuation. This dynamic nature suggests musical possibility.

A quantum harmonic oscillator can be described by its eigenstates, or possible energy levels. The wavefunction of the quantum harmonic oscillator is a linear combination (or superposition) of these eigenstates. The wavefunction is complex-valued and rotates in the complex plane (phase increments). Each eigenstate, then, can interfere based on their phase components in a superposed state. This creates a time-dependent morphing wave and it was this evolving wave pattern that inspired creation of QHOSYN.

QHOSYN can simulate the quantum harmonic oscillator in a superposition of up to 15 eigenstates. It is both a simulation and a tool for generating quantum-based sound. Several sonification strategies were explored (described in section 4). In the most direct sonification, the quantum harmonic oscillator itself is used as a waveform for wavetable synthesis. Beyond this is a stochastic strategy based on the time-varying probability distributions of the quantum harmonic oscillator's wavefunctions. Thus, this work is close in spirit to Xenakis' pioneering work incorporating stochastic theory into musical composition [3].

Copyright: © 2022 Rodney DuPlessis. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

¹ This paper includes sound and video examples. If you click examples in the text, you will be taken to the corresponding media example online. If you are reading a paper copy of this document, or if your PDF reader does not support hyperlinks, you may navigate to the media examples manually in an internet browser at the following address: <https://rodneyduplessis.com/media-examples/SMC2022>

2. PHYSICS

To begin with the physical simulation, we first calculate the eigenbasis of the quantum harmonic oscillator. This will simplify the process of calculating new wavefunctions, as we need only multiply the wavefunction with each basis vector to obtain a new quantum harmonic oscillator.

The eigenbasis forming our Hilbert space is given by:

$$\psi(x, n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^n n!}} \left(\frac{m\omega}{\pi \hbar} \right)^{1/4} e^{-\frac{m\omega x^2}{2\hbar}} H_n \left(\sqrt{\frac{m\omega}{\hbar}} x \right) \quad (1)$$

where n (an integer) is a unique eigenstate of the system and corresponds to the orthogonal axes in our Hilbert space, x is a position, m is the mass of the oscillator, ω is the angular frequency of the oscillator, and H_n are the physicist's Hermite polynomials, which orthogonalize our eigenstates:

$$H_n(x) = (-1)^n e^{x^2} \frac{d^n}{dx^n} e^{-x^2} \quad (2)$$

Using nondimensionalization, we can normalize the units and simplify the problem. We can factor out the reduced Planck constant \hbar as well as the mass and angular frequency of the oscillator, resulting in the simplified equation:

$$\psi(x, n) = \frac{\pi^{1/4}}{\sqrt{2^n n!}} \cdot e^{-(x^2/2)} \cdot H_n \quad (3)$$

This is the form that QHOSYN uses to determine the basis. QHOSYN calculates a 15-dimensional Hilbert space as the eigenbasis for our wavefunction, since we plan to allow up to the first 15 eigenstates to be simulated. This Hilbert space is calculated using the formula described above.

The `WaveFunction` class takes as arguments in its constructor an object of class `HilbertSpace` and an `std::function` that takes a double precision float and returns a double precision float. In its constructor, the `WaveFunction` then calculates an orthogonal basis projection from this `HilbertSpace`.

The wavefunction $\langle \psi |$ given by the user is projected onto the orthogonal vectors $|\phi\rangle$ of the Hilbert space. This entails a matrix multiplication for each energy eigenstate $|\phi\rangle$ that we wish to simulate:

$$\langle \psi_x | \phi_x \rangle = \psi_0 \phi_0 + \psi_1 \phi_1 + \psi_2 \phi_2 + \dots + \psi_n \phi_n \quad (4)$$

The `orthogonalBasisProjection()` method creates a lambda function for each dimension of the Hilbert space. This lambda function takes a float value, samples the Hilbert space in that basis, gets the complex conjugate of the sampled result, and returns the magnitude of that conjugate multiplied by a sample of the wavefunction. In pseudo-code this looks like:

```
float X =
conjugate(hilbertSpace[dimension][x])
* waveFunction[x]
```

This function is then integrated over the integration interval of -10 to 10 in each basis to find the coefficient for each eigenstate. For this, the CQUAD doubly-adaptive integration method from the GNU Scientific Library is used [10]. A normalization factor is then calculated to bring the resulting wavefunction into a usable amplitude range. The resulting wavefunction is a complex valued projection of the superimposed eigenstates. Specifically it is a discretized version of what would be a continuous function, in order to be computable. The spatial resolution of this discretization is 256. This number was chosen as it is a reasonable length to use as a waveform in wavetable synthesis or as a complex array in Fourier synthesis, and it is lean enough to enable fast calculations and broadcasting via OSC.

Once all of the above is finished, the wavefunction is now stored in memory. Every step of the simulation needs only to lookup the value for each position along the x axis at time step t in each orthogonal vector and add the results:

$$\langle \psi(x, t) | = \sum_{n=0}^N c_n \phi_{n,x} t (0.5 + n) i \quad (5)$$

Time t is multiplied by the eigenstate number (energy level). This gives us the imaginary part of our complex number. The value of x at time t for each $|\phi\rangle$ is multiplied by the coefficient c_n for that vector derived from the orthogonal basis projection or given manually by the user. This gives us our wavefunction at every step of the simulation. To obtain the probability distribution, the wavefunction is simply squared.

QHOSYN also provides a means to "measure" the quantum harmonic oscillator. This measurement reveals the true position of the simulated particle represented by the quantum harmonic oscillator based on its probability distribution. A measurement like this would normally collapse the wavefunction of the quantum object through a process called decoherence. In QHOSYN, the effects of decoherence are deliberately ignored in order to maintain the simulation in a state of quantum superposition. This is a somewhat idealized system, similar to that of quantum computing researchers, who try to maintain qubits in a coherent state to preserve the pertinent quantum effects [11].

3. VISUAL INTERFACE

The visual interface of QHOSYN is comprised of the visualization of the quantum harmonic oscillator and several control panels that can be used to configure the simulation, the visualization and sonification, and manage data flow (see figure 1). The visual interface updates at 60 frames per second. User input is accepted via mouse and keyboard.

The visualization of the quantum harmonic oscillator is the dominant element of the interface. The wavefunction itself is represented by a red line. The probability distribution calculated from the wavefunction is a blue line. The three axes (x, y, z) are white lines and a grid is drawn in dark gray lines. If the probability noise band or inverse Fourier transform modes are activated, then the waveform

Figure 1. The visual interface of QHOSYN.

Figure 2. The Draw Panel.

Figure 3. The Simulation Panel.

of those sonifications appear in yellow and cyan, respectively. Any of these visualizations can be activated or deactivated in the "Draw" control panel (figure 2). This allows the user to customize the visualization according to their preference.

The wavefunction evolves over time, its phase rotating and, if the wavefunction is not in a stationary state, its shape changing. The speed of the simulation can be adjusted in the "Simulation" panel (figure 3). The speed can be set between -5 and 5 and is a multiplier on the simulation speed. A speed of 0 will freeze the simulation.

In the simulation panel, the user can also change the number of eigenstates being simulated (between 1 and 15). The basis eigenfunction can be changed from the "Function" dropdown menu. There are currently five presets representing the following eigenfunctions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\phi(x)\rangle &= \sin(x) \\
 |\phi(x)\rangle &= if(x = MaxEigenstate, 1, 0) \\
 |\phi(x)\rangle &= rand(0, 1) \\
 |\phi(x)\rangle &= x - 2 \\
 |\phi(x)\rangle &= \frac{1}{x + 1}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{6}$$

If the user selects "custom" from the Function dropdown menu, a text box will appear into which the user can input a c-style math function. QHOSYN can parse a wide array of arithmetic operators and trigonometric functions (the user can click the "help" button for syntax hints). When the user presses enter after inputting a function, QHOSYN automatically parses the text input into a format that can be applied to the simulation.

Figure 4. The Measurement Panel.

Figure 5. The OSC Panel

The Simulation panel also allows the user to set the coefficients of each eigenstate manually if the "Manual Coefficient Entry" checkbox is selected. The user can also choose to apply the selected function directly to the eigenstate coefficients without orthogonal basis projection by de-selecting the "Project in Orthogonal Basis" checkbox.

Measurements of the wavefunction can be taken by using the controls in the "Measurement" panel (figure 4). A single measurement can be taken by clicking the "Measure" button, or measurements can automatically be taken at a regular interval by activating the "Auto-measure" checkbox and selecting a measurement interval using the Interval slider. When taking measurements, the probability curve of the wavefunction provides a random discrete weighted distribution function. The result of this stochastic sampling is visually displayed on the interface by a white glowing point on the x-axis, indicating the measured position of the particle. This measurement can in turn be sent out via Open Sound Control (OSC) to another application, or control the panner within QHOSYN's sound engine.

The "OSC" panel provides controls for configuring the OSC sending and receiving capabilities of QHOSYN (figure 5). By selecting the "OSC Sender On" checkbox, the controls for OSC sending are revealed (the same for the "OSC Receiver On" checkbox). These controls allow the user to configure the IP address and Port over which to send the OSC messages, the argument to use to identify measurement messages from QHOSYN, whether to send measurement data, and whether to send the entire waveform (as an array).

The "Audio" panel contains the controls for QHOSYN's sound engine (figure 6). Audio can be toggled using the "Audio On" checkbox, and the volume of the audio output can be set with the "Volume" slider. The "Panner" checkbox activates the panner, which pans the sound according to the measurement results (auto-measure must be on). Both audio channels are panned independently. "Channel 1 Source" and "Channel 2 Source" dropdown

Figure 6. The Audio Panel

menus allow the user to select the sources for these channels from the following options: none, Real Wavetable, Imaginary Wavetable, Probability Wavetable, Probability Noise Band, and Inverse Fourier Transform. The "Frequency" slider controls the frequency of wavetable synthesis, and the "Start Bin" and "Bandwidth" sliders control the Fourier transform.

4. SOUND ENGINE

The internal synthesis engine of QHOSYN converts the quantum harmonic oscillator into sound in three ways: wavetable synthesis, inverse Fourier transform synthesis, and noise band synthesis. More possibilities emerge by pairing QHOSYN with an external application through OSC communication. In all cases, the sound is directly derived from the model of the quantum harmonic oscillator.

The wavetable synthesizer (see Video Example 1) is the most direct method of sonifying the wavefunction of the quantum harmonic oscillator. This method uses the oscillating shape of the wavefunction as an evolving waveform. QHOSYN reads through the waveform a number of times per second determined by the value of the Frequency slider set by the user. The wavetable can be derived from the real values of the wavefunction (y axis), the imaginary values (the z axis), or the probability distribution (the magnitude squared of the wavefunction). The wavetable reader always proceeds from left to right on the x axis. When the synthesizer read head reaches the end of the waveform, it wraps back around to the beginning. If the read head lands between sampled values of the wavefunction, it linearly interpolates between the preceding and succeeding sample. The waveform is updated 60 times per second, at the visual frame rate of QHOSYN.

The wavefunction is stored in memory as an array of 256 complex numbers for each time step. The inverse Fourier transform method of synthesizing the wavefunction treats these arrays as frames of a Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT). An STFT breaks a signal into blocks and applies a Fast Fourier Transform algorithm to each block, returning a series of complex-valued arrays that represent slices

of the signal in time. These complex arrays provide information about the frequency, magnitude, and phase content of the signal. One can convert this STFT representation of the signal back into a time-domain signal through an Inverse Short-Time Fourier Transform (ISTFT) process. The inverse Fourier synthesis of QHOSYN takes advantage of the morphological similarity between the data of the wavefunction and the STFT. The sonic result resembles a band-limited impulse train with an evolving spectral envelope (see Video Example 2 and Sound Example 1).

An extension of this technique leads to the noise band synthesis method of QHOSYN. This method follows the same procedure of taking the IFFT of the wavefunction data, except that it randomizes the phase. First, the magnitude of each complex number is taken ($mag = \sqrt{im^2 + re^2}$). Then a random phase is calculated and the real part of the bin is calculated ($re = \cos(phase) * mag$) and the imaginary part is calculated ($im = \sin(phase) * mag$). The IFFT is then taken from this data. The result of this method is colored noise with a spectrum shaped by the probability distribution curve of the wavefunction, shifting and morphing in time (see Video Example 3 and Sound Example 2).

Beyond these synthesis algorithms, another sonic effect was derived from the wavefunction's stochastic nature: The panner. One of the most important purposes of the quantum harmonic oscillator model is to describe the probability of finding a quantum object in a particular eigenstate. In the simplest example, the eigenstate we are looking for is position. The particle has an indeterminate position, and the wavefunction tells us the probability of finding it in any given position. This leads to the idea of measuring the wavefunction by sampling the probability distribution to generate stochastic panning data. A key feature of this stochastic data is that it is not only based on a physical model, but this model describes a non-stationary probability distribution.

The panner can be applied to all of the synthesis methods described here (see Video Example 4). The panner relies on the measurement sampler, which returns a value from the weighted probability distribution of the wavefunction. Each of the two channels gets a different value. Regardless of which synthesis method is chosen, the sound will be panned in the stereo field according to the position measurement.

5. QHOSYN IN SITU

QHOSYN was used heavily in the composition of the author's fixed media electroacoustic work *Psi*.

There are many ways in which quantum harmonic oscillators can be used to generate sound and musical material. *Psi* makes use of at least six methods: the two Fourier methods (the IFFT method and the colored noise method) mentioned in the previous section, the wavetable synthesis method, quantum panning, and two granular paradigms.

The sound material of *Psi* consists of a high-quality recording of a Newton's Cradle, and over 90 unique sound files generated using QHOSYN. Some of the sound files use QHOSYN's internal synthesis, while others use

QHOSYN's OSC data to control another application. The sounds generated with QHOSYN incurred very little post-processing, if any, so that the link to the quantum sound is preserved.

5.1 Wavetable Synthesis

The wavetable synthesis method of sonifying the wavefunction proved to be quite musically inspiring and was further enhanced through spatial effects using stochastic data generated by sampling the wavefunction's probability curve (see Sound Example 3).

It turns out that the most obvious aural effect of the wavetable synthesis is actually the shifting momentum of the particle, not the position. The Fourier transform of a time-varying signal gives us a frequency domain signal from which we can derive the magnitude of a frequency in the original signal. On the other hand, the Fourier transform of a position-varying wave function gives us a momentum curve, the magnitude of which gives us the probability distribution of possible momenta. Time is to frequency as position is to spatial frequency. The phase of a sound signal varies over time whereas the phase of a wavefunction varies over position. The derivative of phase with respect to time (the rate of change of phase over time) is equal to frequency. The derivative of phase with respect to position (the rate of change of phase over position) is equal to spatial frequency. Treating the wave function as a table for wavetable synthesis essentially converts the position axis to a time axis.

The spatial frequency of the Fourier transform becomes temporal frequency. Thus, the evolving spectrum we hear is analogous to the evolving momentum distribution over time. The spectrum is harmonic due to the quantized nature of the energy states of a particle. The energy states in superposition are integer multiples of the ground state,

5.2 Granular Synthesis

Granular synthesis is an apt framework for the sonification of quantum processes. Just as quantum physics explores the most infinitesimal objects in the universe, granular synthesis allows composers to create music using the smallest sonic particles. For the granular explorations of quantum physics in *Psi*, two software applications helped to extend the capabilities of QHOSYN: EmissionControl2, and Pulsar .

EmissionControl2 provided a broad field of possibilities to explore with its 15 parameters, unlimited sound file granulation, and flexible modulation scheme [12]. Measurements of the particle's position in QHOSYN controlled via OSC parameters of EmissionControl2. One of the most direct mappings was to apply these measurements to panning, so that spatial measurements applied to spatial effects in the sound.

Granular synthesis also afforded a metaphor with wave-particle duality. Sonic particles, after all, are actually waves, though they have finite bounds in time and space. Additionally, sound particles make up a Gestalt in granular synthesis that itself might be perceived as wave-like or particulate. Throughout *Psi* wave-particle duality is evoked by

sounds and grain streams in the frequency range at the edge of perception between rhythm and pitch (15-25 Hz). In this range, the listener sometimes perceives individual grains, and sometimes perceives a low frequency wave formed from the fusing of grains.

5.2.1 Pulsar Synthesis

Pulsar synthesis is a method of granular synthesis that emits grains at a regular interval. The pulsar is made up of a "pulsaret" followed by a silent interval. The composer can generate musical sounds by controlling the proportion of pulsaret to silence in the pulsar, the waveform of the pulsaret, the amplitude envelope, and the frequency of the pulsar stream [13]. The author created Pulsar in 2018 to explore the possibilities of this technique in Pure Data [14]. A major benefit of Pulsar in the case of composing for Psi was the ability to flexibly apply data to the parameters thanks to the Pure Data environment.

Pulsar synthesis presents an especially compelling analogy for the perception of the quantum mechanical system in question. With its short, regular pulses, a sampling of the quantum oscillator applied to some of the parameters of pulsar synthesis quickly immerses the listener into the quantum world (see Sound Example 4). Two Pulsar objects were instantiated in Pure Data, and measurement data from QHOSYN was sent to each of them to control their panning. The routing alternated so that the two pulsars did not change position at the same time. The wavefunction of the quantum harmonic oscillator itself provided the waveform of the pulsars. The real part of the wavefunction went to one pulsaret waveform, and the imaginary part to the other (see figure ??). Pulsar synthesis is commonly done with a static pulsaret waveform [13]. This method resulted in a novel form of pulsar synthesis with dynamic pulsaret waveforms that evolve smoothly in time.

5.2.2 3D QHO Granular Clouds

Three instances of QHOSYN can simulate a three-dimensional quantum harmonic oscillator, analogous to a real particle, taking advantage of the fact that the dimensional terms are separable in the three-dimensional Schrödinger equation [15]. For some of the sound material in Psi, such a configuration was used and the measurement data from all three were sent to EmissionControl2 (see Figure ?? and Video Example 5). The x-axis measurement results governed the stereo panning of grains. The y-axis measurement controlled the pitch of grains by modulating the Playback Rate parameter. The z-axis measurements affected the a sense of "depth" of the grains by modulating the Grain Duration and at the same time modulating the filter Resonance (higher z value resulted in longer and more filtered grains, lower z created shorter and less filtered grains).

Using this configuration, it was possible to create three-dimensional quantum granular clouds. This method approached a kind of sonification of a particle in 3D space measured at regular intervals. Under this correspondence, each grain represents the particle in the spatial location it is found each time it is measured. While each measurement

represents the particle at a time and place, a collapsing of the positional potential of the particle, the sonic result is not a well-defined particle. The perception, with so many rapid measurements, is rather a Gestalt mass or cloud of sound that loses definition and takes on a fuzzy character. Thus, the resulting granular clouds contain traces of the quantum probability cloud.

By manually controlling other parameters such as Grain Rate, Asynchronicity, Intermittency, Filter Center, and Envelope Shape, a variety of quantum cloud textures were created. Naturally, the choice of which sound file to granulate had an impact on the quantum cloud texture as well. This sound material included some of the sound files generated from QHOSYN's internal sound engine for Psi as well as the recording of the Newton's Cradle that is featured in the piece.

5.3 Quantum Panning

One of the foundational musical ideas of Psi is a spatial one. The indeterminate position of quantum particles is among their most noteworthy qualities. QHOSYN's ability to take periodic measurements of its quantum harmonic oscillator simulation allows one to generate a stream of evolving stochastic panning data, imbuing any sound with this quantum quality of indeterminate position.

In Psi, this quantum panning effect is applied to most of the sound generated with the synthesis strategies discussed in this section. The rate of measurements taken becomes another synthesis parameter, controlling how frequently the panning is updated.

6. CONCLUSION

Sonification and musification of scientific data and frameworks creates opportunities and poses challenges for the composer. Physics in particular is perhaps the most accommodating of the translation into music of all the sciences. It may be because of the tangibility of the theoretical models, though that aspect does not apply to quantum physics. Certainly any dynamical time-varying theory will lend itself to sonification as music is a dynamic, time-varying art form. Some models in science are static descriptions of a system, and these models tend to lead to musical dead-ends. The most musical scientific models describe the way multiple objects or agents interact over time. From a model such as this, contrapuntal relationships, dynamic gestures, and shifting hierarchies can be derived that naturally propel music forward.

The quantum harmonic oscillator simulated by QHOSYN is such a model. It is also a basic and fundamental model of quantum mechanics that is used as a building block in more elaborate theories. With the initial version of QHOSYN, it was desirable to focus on this most fundamental model to lay the groundwork for more elaborate experiments to come. In a future version of QHOSYN further features and physical models will be explored, such as a collapse mechanic, so that taking a measurement can collapse the wavefunction, followed by dispersion. Other numerical solutions to the time-dependent Schrödinger equa-

tion may allow for real-time user interference in the wave function's evolution. These interferences could cause wave function collapse or trigger creation and annihilation operations (adding or removing energy eigenstates). Lastly, another direction for QHOSYN is to simulate coupled quantum oscillators that might approach a simulation of phonons or quantum fields. Beyond these plans for extending QHOSYN, it will be interesting to see the directions in which other researchers and musicians expand the quantum metaphor in sonification.

Research that extends the quantum harmonic oscillator model described here or that explores other quantum models could reveal a whole new class of time-varying stochastic musical forms. Certainly there is potential in exploring this on the quantum computing machines that are becoming more feasible today. Further possibilities may yet emerge as musicians begin to explore and play with the mathematics, data structures, and paradigms offered by quantum physics. To this end, I have made QHOSYN free and open-source so users can play with the software or probe, modify, and re-purpose the code-base. One can examine the code or download compiled and ready to run versions of the software for Linux, Windows, and MacOS at <https://github.com/rodneypdup/QHOSYN>.

Acknowledgments

The author thanks the following people for inspiration, guidance, and advice that led to the design of QHOSYN: Curtis Roads, Clarence Barlow, João Pedro Oliveira, JoAnn Kuchera-Morin, Mason Hock, Kramer Elwell, Raphael Radna. Parts of this research were supported by a grant from the graduate division of UCSB.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] D. Gabor, "Theory of communication," *Journal of the Institution of Electrical Engineers - Part III: Radio and Communication Engineering*, vol. 93, no. 26, pp. 429–457, 1946. [Online]. Available: <https://digital-library.theiet.org/content/journals/10.1049/ji-3-2.1946.0074>
- [2] —, "Acoustical quanta and the theory of hearing," *Nature*, vol. 159, no. 4044, pp. 591–594, 1947. [Online]. Available: <http://www.nature.com/articles/159591a0>
- [3] I. Xenakis, *Formalized Music: Thought and Mathematics in Composition*. Pendragon Press, 1992, google-Books-ID: y6lL3i0vmMwC.
- [4] C. Roads, *Microsound*. MIT Press, 2002.
- [5] B. L. Sturm, C. Roads, A. McLeran, and J. J. Shynk, "Analysis, visualization, and transformation of audio signals using dictionary-based methods [†]," *Journal of New Music Research*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 325–341, 2009. [Online]. Available: <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09298210903171178>
- [6] R. Fischman, "Clouds, pyramids, and diamonds: Applying Schrödinger's equation to granular synthesis and compositional structure," *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 47–69, 2003. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mitpressjournals.org/doi/abs/10.1162/014892603322022664>
- [7] B. L. Sturm, "Composing for an ensemble of atoms: the metamorphosis of scientific experiment into music," *Organised Sound*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 131–145, 2001. [Online]. Available: https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S1355771801002102/type/journal_article
- [8] L. J. Putnam, J. Kuchera-Morin, and L. Peliti, "Studies in composing hydrogen atom wavefunctions," *Leonardo*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 158–166, 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://www.mitpressjournals.org/doi/10.1162/LEON.a.00912>
- [9] S. J. Ling, J. Sanny, and W. Moebs, "The quantum harmonic oscillator," 2016, book Title: University Physics Volume 3 Publisher: OpenStax. [Online]. Available: <https://opentextbc.ca/universityphysicsv3openstax/chapter/the-quantum-harmonic-oscillator/>
- [10] The GSL Team. Numerical integration — GSL 2.7 documentation. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gnu.org/software/gsl/doc/html/integration.html#cquad-doubly-adaptive-integration>
- [11] K. McCormick. Decoherence is a problem for quantum computing, but ... [Online]. Available: <https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/observations/decoherence-is-a-problem-for-quantum-computing-but/>
- [12] C. Roads, J. Kilgore, and R. DuPlessis, "Architecture for real-time granular synthesis: EmissionControl2," *Manuscript submitted for publication*, p. 27, 2021.
- [13] C. Roads, "Sound composition with pulsars," *Journal of the Audio Engineering Society*, vol. 49, no. 3, pp. 134–147, 2001, publisher: Audio Engineering Society. [Online]. Available: <https://www.aes.org/e-lib/browse.cfm?elib=10198>
- [14] R. DuPlessis, "pulsar~," 2021-10-11, original-date: 2020-04-05T04:24:58Z. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/rodneypdup/pd-pulsar>
- [15] D. M. Fradkin, "Three-dimensional isotropic harmonic oscillator and SU₃," *American Journal of Physics*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 207–211, 1965. [Online]. Available: <http://aapt.scitation.org/doi/10.1119/1.1971373>